

DIRECTION OF ARRIVAL ESTIMATION IN FMCW RADAR USING THE MUSIC-2D ALGORITHM

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Abstract: *This paper presents the MUSIC-2D algorithm applied to determine the angle of targets of the FMCW radar. As a result, figures, two-dimensional heat maps, and Range-Angle (RA) maps are presented. The distance and angle at which the targets are located are observed. A target azimuth accuracy estimation and angular resolution using the Angle DFT and MUSIC-2D algorithms are compared. The system and the signal model are described. Simulations and data processing of several scenarios experimentally determined by the FMCW TDM MIMO commercial radar were performed in MATLAB.*

Keywords: *MUSIC-2D, Angle DFT, FMCW Radar, Range-Angle map.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The need for precise determination of key target parameters - such as range, velocity and angle at which the target is located has led to the widespread use of FMCW radars. The FMCW radars are usually used in medicine (Alizadeh et al., 2019; Bliss et al., 2006), in drone with low radar cross-section detection (de Quevedo et al., 2018), and in the automotive industry (Bilik et al., 2019). Due to its large Time-to-Bandwidth (tB), FMCW radar allows for accurate and precise measurement of target distance and velocity. Moreover, the angular estimation and resolution relate to the antenna aperture and the number of receive antennas (Richards, 2005). In real-world scenarios, due to limited space, cost reduction requirements and hardware resource optimization, the implementation of a large number of receive antennas is often impractical. When using conventional angle estimation algorithms such as Angle DFT, even radars which use multiple transmit antennas and form a virtual antenna array do not provide sufficiently accurate results. For this reason, it is necessary to apply high-resolution algorithms such as MUSIC.

This paper presents the MUSIC applied to determine the angle and distance to the target, resulting in a two-dimensional Range-Angle (RA) map. A system and signal model used for both simulation and experimental verification were presented. In addition, the AngleDFT and MUSIC-2D algorithms are described. Several scenarios are investigated to illustrate the performance of the algorithms, including the accuracy of angle estimation and angular resolution, along with a comparative analysis of the results obtained using the aforementioned algorithms.

2. SISTEM AND SIGNALS MODELS

The system and signals models are described in text that follows. First the time division multiplex (TDM), multiple input multiple output (MIMO), frequency modulated continuous wave FMCW radar system is presented. In addition, two-dimensional complex signals are described.

2.1. System model

A TDM MIMO FMCW radar system consists of two transmit antennas and four receive antennas (Figure 1). The FMCW signal is fed to the transmit antenna via a microwave switch, which controls the antennas, in terms of transmission time. The transmission occurs alternately between the two antennas. After the signal is reflected from the target, it is received by a linear antenna array. The target is assumed to be in the far field, so the reflected signal reaches the receive antennas as a plane wave. The received signal passes through a low noise amplifier (LNA) and is then mixed with the transmitted signal, as well as a version of the same signal

phase-shifted by 90° . An in-phase (I) and quadrature (Q) components are generated in this process. After passing through a low-pass filter, the intermediate frequency (IF) signals are generated and then sampled using an analog-to-digital converter (ADC) and processed using digital signal processing (DSP). The I and Q samples are combined to form complex signal samples. These samples are organized into a three-dimensional Radar Data Cube (RDC), where one axis contains samples originated from one chirp, the other contains multiple chirp samples, and the third axis contains samples of signals received from multiple antennas.

Figure 1: Radar system model

Two separate radar data cubes are formed, each containing samples of a signal from a single transmit antenna. Combination of samples creates a virtual array with one transmit antenna and eight virtual receive antennas; and one RDC is formed. Given the short duration of the chirp (a few milliseconds), it is assumed that the target remains within the same resolution cell, so that Doppler phase compensation is not required. By determining the beat frequency in the IF signal, which depends on the target position, information about the distance is extracted. The delay of the signal over the receive array is used to estimate the angle of arrival (Đaković et al., 2025).

2.2. Signal model

To generate a RA map at a given time, signal samples from a single chirp and multiple receive antennas are analyzed. These samples are analytically represented as a two-dimensional complex exponential signal (Manokhin et al., 2015):

$$Y(m, n) = \sum_{l=1}^L \alpha_l e^{j\varphi_l} e^{j2\pi \frac{2R_l B}{cT_c} mT_s} e^{j\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} d n \sin\theta_l} + n_n(m, n), \quad (1)$$

where $\alpha_l e^{j\varphi_l}$ denotes complex amplitude and phase, R_l is the distance, θ_l is the angle of l -th target out of the L total targets, B is the FMCW signal bandwidth, c is the propagation speed of EM waves (considered equal the speed of light in the air), T_c is the duration of chirp, T_s denotes the sampling period, λ is the wavelength of transmission signal, the distance between receiving antennas is denoted as $d = \lambda/2$, $n_n(n, m)$ is the noise, $n=0 \dots N_{R_x}-1$, where N_{R_x} is the number of receiving antennas and $m=0 \dots N_0-1$, where N_0 denotes the number of samples in the chirp ($N_0 = T_c/T_s$). Matrix of samples is denoted as Y and is of dimension $[N_0 \times N_{R_x}]$.

3. ANGLE DFT AND MUSIC-2D ALGORITHMS

3.1. Angle DFT

The Angle DFT algorithm is usually applied after the Range DFT algorithm, after the bit rate and range of the target have been determined using the Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT). The Angle DFT algorithm is based on the application of the DFT to estimate the phase shift between signals received by multiple receiving antennas. The phase shift is the result of the time delay introduced by the additional path the signal transmits when the target is at a certain angle to the radar (Đaković et al., 2025). The target angle is given as follows:

$$\theta_u = \sin^{-1}\left(u \frac{\lambda}{Nd}\right), \quad (2)$$

where $-\frac{N}{2} \leq u < \frac{N}{2}$, and N represents the number of the DFT coefficients. The measurement range of the angle and angular resolution can be determined as follows:

$$-\sin^{-1}\left(\frac{\lambda}{2d}\right) \leq \theta < \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{\lambda}{2d}\right), \quad (3)$$

$$\theta_{\text{res}} = 2 \cdot \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{\lambda}{2N_{R_x}d \cos(\tilde{\theta})}\right), \quad (4)$$

the central angle $\tilde{\theta}$, is the angle of the target arrival. The angular resolution does not depend on the number of DFT coefficients, but solely on the number of receiving antennas.

3.2. Music-2D

The matrix of the received signals can be determined as in Equation (5).

$$Y = AXS + N, \quad (5)$$

$$A = [a(\theta_1), a(\theta_2), \dots, a(\theta_L)]_{N_{R_x} \times L}, \quad (6)$$

$$a(\theta_l) = [1, e^{-j\frac{2\pi}{\lambda}d\sin(\theta_l)}, \dots, e^{-j\frac{2\pi}{\lambda}d(N-1)\sin(\theta_l)}]_{1 \times N_{R_x}}^T, \quad (7)$$

$$X = \text{diag} [\alpha_1 e^{j\varphi_1}, \alpha_2 e^{j\varphi_2}, \dots, \alpha_L e^{j\varphi_L}]_{L \times L}, \quad (8)$$

$$S = [s(R_1), s(R_2), \dots, s(R_L)]_{N_o \times L}^T, \quad (9)$$

$$s(R_l) = [1, e^{-j2\pi\frac{2R_l B}{cT_c}T_s}, \dots, e^{-j2\pi\frac{2R_l B}{cT_c}(N_o-1)T_s}]_{1 \times N_o}^T, \quad (10)$$

where A is the matrix of the angular steering vector $a(\theta_l)$, X is the diagonal matrix of complex amplitudes and phases of the signal, S is the matrix of the time steering vector $s(R_l)$, and N is the additive noise matrix.

The MUSIC algorithm relies on the singular decomposition of the autocorrelation matrix of the signal C_Y , enabling the distinction between noise and signal subspaces. It is shown that the signal subspace depends on the number of targets. By comparing the steering vector to the noise subspace, the angle of arrival the signal can be estimated with high resolution. The MUSIC-2D algorithm follows further steps (Manokhin et al., 2015):

- Reorganize matrix Y into the column vector \tilde{Y} by stacking all the rows sequentially, into a single column as follows:

$$\tilde{Y} = [Y(1 \dots N_{R_x}, 1), Y(1 \dots N_{R_x}, 2), \dots, Y(1 \dots N_{R_x}, N_o)]_{1 \times N_{R_x}N_o}^T, \quad (11)$$

- Determine the correlation matrix $C_{\tilde{Y}} [N_{R_x}N_o \times N_{R_x}N_o]$:

$$C_{\tilde{Y}} = \frac{1}{N_{R_x}N_o} \tilde{Y} \tilde{Y}^H, \quad (12)$$

- Perform singular value decomposition:

$$C_{\tilde{Y}} = Q \Lambda Q^H, \quad (13)$$

- Determine the number of targets L. It is common practice to compute Range-Doppler matrix firstly. Based on the structure and peak distribution within this matrix, the number of detected targets can be estimated.

- Construct the matrix Q_n , based on matrix Q, such that Q_n contains samples corresponding to the signal subspace.

$$Q_n = [Q(L+1), \dots, Q(N_{R_x}N_o)]_{N_{R_x}N_o \times N_{R_x}N_o-L}, \quad (14)$$

where $Q(n)$, is n^{th} column of matrix Q.

- Determine column vector $V(R, \theta)$:

$$V(R, \theta) = [v(1 \dots N_{R_x}, 1), v(1 \dots N_{R_x}, 2), \dots, v(1 \dots N_{R_x}, N_o)]_{1 \times N_{R_x}N_o}^T, \quad (15)$$

$$v = a(\theta)s(R)^T, \quad (16)$$

- Determine the value of function $P(R, \theta)$:

$$P(R, \theta) = \frac{1}{V(R, \theta)^H Q_n Q_n^H V(R, \theta)}, \quad (17)$$

- Compute the values across all angles and ranges within the search space. Determine the corresponding response matrix and determine the target's range and angle of arrival, based on its maximum value.

4. SIMULATION

For the simulation purposes, a given radar cube was generated using the MIMOFMCW.m function. The radar parameters used in both the simulation and experimental setup are: operating frequency $f_c = 24$ GHz, signal bandwidth $B = 1$ GHz, chirp duration $T_c = 0,5$ ms, sampling frequency $f_s = 64$ KHZ, the number of samples in the chip $N_o = 32$, the number of antennas in the virtual antenna array $N_{R_x} = 8$. The parameters set in this way enable a unique radar range of up to 4.8 m and angle measurement in the range from -90° to 90° . Using the MUSIC method, a resolution step of 0.1 m per distance in 0.5° per angle was taken, which makes

the RA map of dimensions [97 x 361]. Therefore, for fair comparison, the DFT coefficients using the Angle DFT method were calculated for the same number of points.

CASE 1

The target parameters used in the simulation are presented in Table 1. The parameter A denotes the amplitude of the echo signal received from the target, which can be related to the radar reflective surface, r indicates the distance of the target, v is its speed and θ is the angle at which the target is located relative to the radar.

Table 1: Simulation parameters

Target No	A [V]	r [m]	v [m/s]	θ [°]
1	1	4.5	1	70
2	0.8	3	2	-70
3	0.8	3	3	-50
4	0.7	1.5	4	-10
5	0.7	1.5	5	10
6	0.6	0.5	6	0

In this case, the target speed is not considered critical, since the Range-Doppler map is not generated. The targets are generated so that target 1 is positioned at a large observing angle, while target 6 is at a observing angle of 0°. Targets 2 and 3, as in 4 and 5, are arranged in pairs, such that the angular difference between the pairs is equal, but the central angle of arrival for the first pair is equal to 60°, while that of the second pair is equal to 0°. It is considered to be ideal conditions and there is no influence of noise. Figure 2 shows the RA matrix obtained using the RangeDFT algorithm (left), and a heatmap image (right).

Figure 2: RA matrix (left), and RA map (right) (AngleDFT)

The matrix is normalized in accordance with its maximum value, which allows for consistent visual interpretation. By identifying the peak (maximum) values of the lobes, the angle and range of the targets can be determined. It can be concluded that the angles at which the targets are located are estimated with a certain error, because the algorithm does not offer high accuracy, due to the wide main lobes in the spectrum estimation. Due to the width of the lobes in both dimensions, a small error occurs in the range estimation for targets 1, 2 and 3. Targets 2 and 3 were not successfully separated and were located under one lobe, despite having the same angular distance as targets 4 and 5. The consequence was a decrease in the angular resolution with an increase in the viewing angle. Despite a number of targets in the space, the first singular value dominates, because of high correlation between the target signals due to the FMCW radar signal. Figure 3 shows the RA matrix obtained using the MUSIC-2D algorithm (left), and a heatmap image (right).

The maximum of the function very accurately determines the angle at which the target is located. The angle of target 1 is more difficult to determine, due to the large angle of arrival, the spectrum of the signal is mapped to the other end of the matrix. Targets 2 and 3 were not successfully separated because of reduced angular resolution cell. Unlike the previous method, the other parts of the spectrum had a high-level value; the maxima are distributed in the range of 0.6 to 1 of normalized value, so that targets with a low amplitude are more noticeable.

FMCW radars can detect signals even at low signal-to-noise ratios (SNR) (Simić, 2007). Figure 4 shows the RA maps corresponding to SNR levels of 5 dB, 0 dB, and -5 dB. It is shown that the MUSIC-2D algorithm is more sensitive to noise, compared to the AngleDFT algorithm, and already at 0 dB SNR ratios, lower amplitude targets cannot be detected.

Figure 3: RA matrix (left) and RA map (right) (MUSIC-2D)

Figure 4: RA maps: a) AngleDFT, SNR = 5 dB, b) AngleDFT, SNR = 0 dB, c) AngleDFT, SNR = -5 dB, d) MUSIC-2D, SNR = 5 dB, e) MUSIC-2D, SNR = 0 dB, f) MUSIC-2D, SNR = -5 dB

At low SNR values, target visibility can be improved if they are highlighted. This procedure involves subtracting the mean value of the matrix from each element, which suppresses the dominant background values, while emphasizing the regions containing real targets. Afterwards, the rows corresponding to the target ranges have to be normalized with respect to the maximum value of each row. Data on the distance of the target can be determined from the Range-Doppler map (Manokhin et al., 2015).

CASE 2

In Case 2, only targets with low normalized amplitudes (0.6 and 0.5) are simulated, positioned at angles of -50° and 40° , with a SNR=-5 dB. As in the previous case, the MUSIC-2D algorithm estimates the angle more precisely, and targets remain detectable even at lower amplitude and SNR levels, which suggests that the efficiency of the MUSIC-2D algorithms is affected by the number of targets (Figure 5).

Figure 5: RA map AngleDFT (left) and RA map MUSIC-2D (right)

5. EXPERIMENTAL VERIFICATION

The Luswave MIMO radar platform PUP_DUAL24P_T2R4 was used to conduct the experiments. The platform generates the FMCW waveforms and allows changing parameters such as duration, number of samples in the chirp, operating frequency, frequency range of the signal, and similar (Luswave, 2020). The target was a man moving towards the radar at an angle of approximately -30° . In he carried a Lunenberg lens, a radar reflector, to amplify the reflection of the signal.

Figure 5: Experimental results: RA map AngleDFT (left) and RA map MUSIC-2D (right)

6. CONCLUSION

The MUSIC-2D algorithm was tested and compared to the AngleDFT algorithm in terms of determining the angle of target using FMCW radar. The MUSIC-2D algorithm is shown to be more accurate and computationally complex, and more sensitive to noise compared to the AngleDFT algorithm. By applying this algorithm, the angular resolution does not increase significantly, but still depends on the number of receiving antennas. Due to the high correlation and similarity between FMCW echo signals and with a larger number of targets, it is more difficult to detect targets of low amplitude. The AngleDFT proved to be a robust algorithm, which estimates the target angle with noticeable errors. However, its implementation is simpler and at low SNR ratios, and it detects low amplitude targets more successfully. Further research can be directed towards more advanced algorithms such as Decorrelation Algorithms, Spatial Smoothing, or Forward-Backward Averaging.

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